

Contextual Scaffolding and Literal Comprehension of Grade Two Pupils in Their Home Language

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Abstract. This study investigated the impact of contextual scaffolding on the literal comprehension skills of Grade Two pupils in their home language at Binugao Central Elementary School, Division of Davao Del Sur. Using a quasi-experimental design with non-equivalent control groups, the research involved 45 pupils divided into a control group (23 pupils) and an experimental group (22 pupils). The study employed a blended learning modality with both online sessions and printed modules. Pre- and post-tests measured the literal comprehension skills of the pupils. Findings indicated that the experimental group, which received contextual scaffolding, showed a significant improvement in their post-test scores compared to the control group. The results demonstrated that contextual scaffolding significantly enhanced literal comprehension, with the experimental group advancing from the 'Beginning' to the 'Approaching Proficiency' level. The study highlighted the importance of strategic instructional approaches like contextual scaffolding in improving reading comprehension in early education, suggesting its broader application for enhancing literacy skills among young learners.

KEY WORDS

1. Contextual Scaffolding
2. Literal Comprehension
3. Educational Strategies

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1. Introduction

Scaffolding is a teaching technique in which instructors break down lessons into smaller segments, providing less support as students gain mastery of new concepts or material. Similar to scaffolding on a building, this technique gives students a framework for learning as they develop and strengthen their understanding. Once students achieve the desired level of comprehension or mastery, the teacher can gradually step back and remove their support.

The scaffolding approach differs from the traditional "independent learning" model, where a teacher assigns students tasks such as reading an article for homework or writing a

five-page essay without providing additional structured support. While students can ask questions in this scenario, many may feel hesitant to do so. Navigating through new course content independently may prove challenging for students who don't learn well via independent study.

Before scaffolding a lesson on new material, teachers must ensure that students have the necessary background knowledge, which could include basic, foundational information. For example, when introducing a lesson on the Boston Tea Party, the teacher should confirm that their students understand where Boston is located,

what taxes are, why tea was important at the time, and why Britain might be concerned if a shipment of tea ends up in Boston Harbor. The phrase "No taxation without representation!" holds little meaning if students don't grasp the significance of each word. Scaffold learning is a term that refers to the process of providing students with temporary or partial support to help them complete a task or reach a goal. The support can come in the form of physical scaffolding, like a ladder or platform that allows someone to climb to a higher level, or it can be more abstract, like providing hints or clues to help solve a problem. One of the best ways to scaffold learning is to pre-teach vocabulary. When students are familiar with the words they will be using, they can focus on understanding the meaning of the words instead of trying to figure out what they mean. Pre-teaching also helps build vocabulary skills, which will be useful throughout the student's academic career. Modelling is another scaffolding strategy that teachers can use to introduce new material. When you model a task, you show students how to do it through demonstrations, verbal explanations, or written instructions. After you have modelled the task, give students a chance to practice it. It will help them understand and apply the material in their own lives. Scaffolding holds promise in allowing teachers to assist students without diminishing the cognitive challenge of tasks. Goos, Galbraith and Renshaw (2022) described scaffolding as "mutual adjustment and appropriation of ideas rather than a simple transfer of information and skills from teacher to learner". However, effective scaffolding remains a difficult task for teachers. In their study of scaffolding in classrooms, Bliss, Askew, and Macrae (2023) found many instances of "missed scaffolds" (p. 48) where "conditions for scaffolding were present but not noticed by the teacher. In these instances, "pupils are crying out to be scaffolded". It is such instances that I have

described as "scaffolding opportunities". Scaffolding opportunities are similar to teachable moments. Teachable moments have been described as "the set of behaviours within a lesson that indicated that students are ripe for, or receptive to, learning because they express confusion, misunderstanding, uncertainty, struggle, or difficulty with a mathematical problem, concept or procedure" (Arafeh, Smerdon Snow, 2021). Muir (2021) described teachable moments as "a teacher's simultaneous act in response to a student's answer, comment or suggestion and is utilized to either address a possible misconception or to enhance conceptual understanding". Effectively dealing with teachable moments as they arise demands teachers have a high level of mathematical knowledge for teaching. Responding to teachable moments or scaffolding opportunities is a difficult task. Two key factors emerged in my study that appeared crucial in determining if a scaffolding opportunity was taken or missed. These were teacher knowledge and use of appropriate materials to illustrate concepts, and the teacher responding appropriately to the students' prior knowledge. (Muir, 2021) Meanwhile, many students struggle with reading comprehension, which can seriously strain a child throughout all classroom subjects. Because learning all academic content requires reading in some form, students who struggle with reading comprehension often need to catch up to their classmates academically in multiple areas. Fortunately, there are ways to help struggling students. Sometimes the reasons for difficulties in reading comprehension can be unknown to parents. The underlying cause may be an undiagnosed learning disorder or a child's stress that the parent is not aware of. Like other learning differences, reading comprehension problems are often a hidden disability. Parents, teachers, and peers may be unaware that someone is struggling with this issue, especially when their reading proficiency seems fine otherwise. Kids and adults with reading compre-

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

hension disorders are no less smart than their peers. People with comprehension challenges have general learning ability that is as high as, or higher than, those without learning disabilities. They simply have a deficit in this single area. By getting help to improve their grasp on what they read, children can become more confident and capable in school and beyond. Reading comprehension skills can influence a student’s performance in the classroom and later in the workplace. Offering early interventions and providing support can help those struggling

with comprehension problems succeed—and get more enjoyment from reading. In the Division of Davao Del Sur particularly in Binugao Central Elementary School, children can read but struggle to understand what they read. They need to understand the word’s meaning in their context to grasp it fully. Therefore, scaffolding is needed so that learners will comprehend the text they read. The researcher being teacher in the early grade explored scaffolding as a strategy to help learners understand what they read and eventually appreciate the story.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure

and the data analysis. It is also worth noting that artificial intelligence was used in the proofreading of this paper, this statement is an additional ethical practice in the era of AI in research.

2.1. —Conceptual Framework of the Study

2.2. *Research Design*—This study made use of the quasi-experimental research design which was a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design was a good design when the researcher had ac-

cessed to one group for experimentation (Vockel 2021). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study were intact group of learners. This design was represented as follows:

$$O_1 \quad x \quad O_2$$

$$O_3 \quad x \quad O_4$$

Where:

O_1 - Pretest of the experimental group

O_2 - Posttest of the experimental group

O_3 - Pretest of the controlled group

O_4 - Posttest of the controlled group

--- - Non-random assignment of subjects

X - Treatment applied in the experimental group

Fig. 2. Enter Caption

2.3. *Research Respondents*—This study was the experimental group. The composition was conducted in Binugao Central Elementary School, Division of Davao Del /Sur. The subjects of this study were the 45 grade two pupils – 23 were from section A which was the controlled group and 22 were from section B which both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study.

Distribution of Respondents

Subjects	No. of Pupils	Total
1. Section A	23	
2. Section B	22	
<i>Total</i>	45	

2.4. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It was a blended learning where teacher gave module at the same meet the learners online but adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher had to meet the learners online for a follow up session of what had been printed in the module. The pre and post-performance test consist of a 25 –item test was eventually determine the literal comprehension skills of the research subjects. The pretest was administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest was very helpful to assess the literal comprehension skills of the grade two learners. On the hand, posttest was administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the level of the literal comprehension skills of the grade two learners, the following continuum was used based on DepEd rating system

Performance Level Criteria

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understandings, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge, skills, and core understandings, and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge, skills, and core understandings, and with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge, skills, and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher drafted a letter seeking for permission that this research study was conducted were sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City, Dr. Reynante A. Solitario, CESO V and the school principal of Binugao Central Elementary School. While letters seeking permission were delivered to the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and had it validated by the experts preferably the

experts of the study. After permission had been granted that this study be conducted in Binugao Central Elementary School and after the research questionnaire had been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher was administered pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commences her experiment. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher was administered posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects were submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher made analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—

The following statistical tools was used in the analysis and interpretation the responses in this study. Mean was used to describe the level of the literal comprehension skills in both

pretest and posttest scores. Eta square was used to measure the magnitude of contextual scaffolding on the literal comprehension skills of the grade two learners

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the discussion of the problems in this study. They were discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship

of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores. Pre-Test Score of Learners Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade nine students. The controlled group got the mean of 16.30 or Beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 17.10 or Beginning.

Table 1. Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Controlled Group				
	n	mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Pre-test	23	16.30	65.2	Beginning
Experimental Group				
	n	mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Pre-test	22	17.10	68.4	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group had a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs Beginning level. This finding was congruent to the idea of Lytle (2002) who said that an instructor who used instructional scaffolding became more of a mentor and facilitator of knowledge than the dominant content expert. This teaching style provided the incentive for students took more active role in their own learning. Students shared the responsibility of teaching and learning through scaffolds that required them to moved beyond their current skill and knowledge levels. Through this interaction, students were able to take ownership of the learning event. Scaffolding had become a key concept in education. It was a framework to described an adults' supportive role in children's

learning. Scaffolding enabled a child to solved a problem, carried out a tasked or achieved a goal which was just beyond his or her abilities. During play, where foundational social and emotional skills were developed, scaffolding was a bridge to new skill levels used three key ingredients; modeling the skill, giving clues and asking questions while the child is trying out a new skill, and then as the child approached mastery, withdrawing the support (Vygotsky, 2023).

Shown in table 2 were the post-test scores of the grade nine students. The controlled group got the mean of 20.10 or Developing while the experimental group gained the mean of 21.03 or Approaching Proficiency. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group had a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase

of 3.93 from a mean rating of 17.10 to 21.03. better performance than the controlled group. This means that experimental group had a far

Table 2. Post-Test Score of Pupils

Controlled Group				
	n	mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Post-test	23	20.10	80.40	Developing
Experimental Group				
	n	mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Post-test	22	21.03	84.12	Approaching Proficiency

This finding was congruent to the idea of Ross (2021) who cited that as teachers worked within their classrooms to developed lessons, activities, and demonstrations to extended the literacy learning of their students, they must constantly strive to met the diverse needed of their students by selecting and implementing a variety of instructional models and materials. Many teachers had found that their knowledge of each student’s competencies allowed them to adjusted lessons and supported each student as they extended that student’s literacy learning. Since the ideas talked about on how to address or improved students’ performance task, an instructional innovation or intervention in teaching MAPEH was introduced. Similar to the scaffolding used in construction supported workers as they worked on a specific task, instructional scaffolds were temporary support structured faculty put in place assisted students

in accomplishing new tasks and concepts they could not typically achieved on their own. “As students begun to demonstrate task mastery, the assistance or support is decreased gradually in order to shift the responsibility for learning from the [instructor] to the student” (San Jose Evergreen Community College District, 2023). Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post- Test Score. Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.47 with a p-value of .0373 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the grade two pupils. This implied that contextual scaffolding in had contributed the effectiveness in literal comprehension of grade two pupils in their home language which was revealed by the scores of the grade two pupils.

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	39	-5.47	.0373	Significant

This finding was in line with the statement of Hensen (2021) who said that scaffolding means that the teacher, another adult,

or classmate provided temporary support for the learner(s). Scaffolding was compared with learning to ride a bike. Various authors (e.g.,

Cooper, 2021; Dorn, 2023, etc.) had viewed scaffolding as analogous to learning new motor skills, such as bike riding. The new bike rider was held and pushed by a helper through the motor activity of getting on and pedaling and being steadied while making multiple attempts until balance and control was achieved. Feedback from self and others was ongoing. Individuals, be they an adult, a more knowledgeable peer, or a parent, work within this zone to support a child until she/he was able to internalized and demonstrated independent ability or ownership of new learning. The term used to described this support was “scaffolding,” which had been defined as a support system that helped children achieved success on tasks that would be too difficult for them to achieve by themselves (Wood, Bruner, Ross, 2023)

Table 4 highlights the test of contextualize scaffolding on the literal comprehension of grade two pupils on their home language. It generated an Eta² value of 0.426 which signifies large effect. This implies that teachers should look for a strategy in using contextualize scaffolding for literal comprehension of grade two pupils in their home language. scaffolding is a crucial instructional technique that enhances teaching and learning by providing the necessary support for students to achieve their full potential. It bridges the gap between existing knowledge and new learning, promotes higher-order thinking and problem-solving, engages students in active learning, supports differentiated instruction, and facilitates the gradual transfer of responsibility to students.

Table 4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Grade 2 Pupils

N	t-value	Eta²	Descriptive Value	Decision
45	-4.33	0.426	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Scaffolding was a dynamic and responsive teaching approach that supports students through the learning process. By providing appropriate levels of assistance and gradually removed this support, teachers helped students developed the skills and confidence needed to

become independent, successful learners. This method not only enhances academic achievement but also fosters a deeper understanding and appreciation of the learning process (Beed,P.,Hawkins,M.,(2021).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displayed the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made. This study sought to determine the effect of contextual scaffolding on literal comprehension of grade two learners. This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation. The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners.

4.1. Findings—This study was conducted in Binugao Central Elementary School, Binu-

gao District Division of Davao City. The subjects of this study were the 45 grade two pupils

– 23 were from section A which was the controlled group and 22 were from section B which was the experimental group. The composition of these two sections was homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of contextual scaffolding on literal comprehension of grade two learners had improved the academic performance of the learners. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions were drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade two learners both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group are at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Approaching level.

4.3. *Recommendations*—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching grade two should use contextual scaffolding on literal comprehension as a strategic approach. English teachers can adopt to maximize the effectiveness of contextual scaffolding in

enhancing students' literal comprehension. contextual scaffolding focused on English literal comprehension for grade two students can be highly beneficial. A camp setting can provide an immersive experience where students focus intensely on language skills. It allows for more individualized attention and tailored instruction to meet the specific needs of each student, especially those who might be struggling. The school heads should promote the use of contextual scaffolding for literal comprehension of grade two learners. These intensive, immersive programs offer a unique environment for language acquisition, and English teachers play a pivotal role in their success. Combining immersive experiences, intensive practice, interactive learning methods, and continuous assessment to foster significant improvements in participants' language abilities. A school policy on promoting the use of a contextual scaffolding for literal comprehension can be issued. Besides, the said program can be highly beneficial for students. He can invite the teacher-researcher to demo teach during LAC session using social interaction as a strategy in teaching to ensure that the teachers running the camp are well-trained For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of contextual scaffolding on literal comprehension as a strategy in teaching will be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

5. References

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